

On the Failure of Classical Approach on Expression for Change in the Density of a Compressible Liquid with Depth

Sourjya Gupta, Subrata Gupta

Student, Officer of Government of West Bengal
Civil Engineering
Techno India University, Kolkata, India

Abstract : This paper derives the change in density of a liquid with depth in a column of that liquid, due to its own weight. The temperature is assumed to be constant. The pressure of the liquid at any level causes it to be compressed. A real liquid is always compressible to a certain extent. The analysis carried out provides an expression for the expected variation of density of a liquid with depth. However, Inter-molecular force of attraction and repulsion causes molecules to maintain an optimum distance from each other. Thus, real liquids assume a minimum volume even under pressure. Computations carried out on the analytical solution shows that the classical approach in treating the liquid fails, when density assumes extremely high values which is not supported by experience. This paper thus demonstrates the failure of classical approach in solving the problem

IndexTerms -Density, Pressure, Linear Differential Equation, Integrating Factor, First Order Differential Equation, Inter-Molecular Distance, Van der Waals radii.

I. INTRODUCTION

WE ASSUME A COLUMN OF LIQUID IN A CONTAINER, AS SHOWN IN FIG. 1. WE FORMULATE THE FORCES ACTING ON ANY ELEMENT OF THE LIQUID AT AN ARBITRARY LEVEL. SHOWS A COLUMN OF LIQUID. WE DEFINE CERTAIN QUANTITIES AS FOLLOWS:

h = Height refers to the height of the column of liquid above an arbitrary level of the liquid.

l – Refers to the height of the liquid from the datum level to the arbitrary level.

F = Force experienced by the liquid at the arbitrary level due to the weight of the liquid above it.

m = Mass of the liquid above the arbitrary level.

g = Acceleration due to gravity

A = Area of cross section of the container

V = Volume of the container

k = Bulk modulus of the liquid

P = Pressure acting on an elemental film of the liquid at the arbitrary level.

ρ = Density of the liquid

Fig (1).

The plain P-P' is at an arbitrary height h from the top of the column of the liquid and at a distance l from the bottom.

H the total height of the liquid in the container and is given by:

$$H = h + l \quad \dots (1)$$

Since Bulk Modulus, k of the liquid is given by,

$$k = -V \frac{dP}{dV} \quad \dots (2)$$

The volume of the liquid till height l is being compressed by the column of liquid above it with height h. The volume of the liquid being compressed is,

$$V = Al \quad \dots (3)$$

Putting the value for V, in eqn (2), we obtain,

$$k = -Al \frac{dP}{dAl} \quad \dots (4)$$

As area of cross section A is constant, we express the pressure on the liquid in terms of force,

Rewriting eqn (4),

$$k = -\frac{l dPA}{A dl}$$

As,

$$F = PA \quad \dots (5)$$

Hence,

$$k = -\frac{l dF}{A dl} \quad \dots (6)$$

We now relate the change in the force experienced by a column of liquid of height l, because of the weight of the column of liquid of height h above it,

$$\frac{dF}{dh} = \frac{dmg}{dh} = \frac{dgv\rho}{dh} = \frac{d\rho hAg}{dh} = Ag \frac{d\rho h}{dh} \quad \dots (7)$$

As area and acceleration due to gravity are constants, those can be taken out of the differential,

And writing $\frac{dF}{dh}$ in terms of $\frac{dF}{dl}$,

$$\frac{dF}{dh} = \frac{dF}{d(H-l)}$$

from which,

$$\frac{dh}{dF} = \frac{d(H-l)}{dF} \quad \dots (8)$$

As as H is a constant $\frac{dH}{dF} = 0$, and we get,

$$\frac{dF}{dh} = -\frac{dF}{dl} \quad \dots (9)$$

Therefore, we can rewrite eqn (6) as,

$$k = \frac{l dF}{A dh} \quad \dots (10)$$

From eqn (7) and eqn (10),

$$k = \frac{l}{A} Ag \frac{d\rho h}{dh} \quad \dots (11)$$

Now from multiplication rule,

$$\frac{d\rho h}{dh} = \frac{hd\rho}{dh} + \rho \quad \dots (12)$$

$$\text{We get, } k = lg \frac{hd\rho}{dh} + lg\rho \quad \dots (13)$$

Since, $h = (H - l)$, rearranging the terms in eqn (13), we have,

$$\frac{k - lg\rho}{lg(H-l)} = \frac{d\rho}{dh} \quad \dots (14)$$

As,

$$\frac{dh}{d\rho} = \frac{d(H-l)}{d\rho}$$

We get,

$$\frac{d\rho}{dh} = -\frac{d\rho}{dl} \quad \dots (15)$$

Now we can write,

$$\frac{k}{lg(H-l)} - \frac{lg\rho}{lg(H-l)} = -\frac{d\rho}{dl} \quad \dots (16)$$

On rearranging we get the final form,

$$\frac{d\rho}{dl} - \frac{\rho}{(H-l)} = -\frac{k}{gl(H-l)} \quad \dots (17)$$

We can see that it is a simple first order linear differential equation of form,

$$\frac{dy}{dx} + P(x)y = Q(x)$$

Where,

$$y = \rho$$

$$x = l$$

$$P(x) = -\frac{1}{H-l}$$

$$Q(x) = -\frac{k}{lg(H-l)}$$

The solution of such a first order linear differential equation is,

$$y = e^{-\int p(x)dx} [\int e^{\int p(x)dx} Q(x)dx + C] \quad \dots (18)$$

The solution to the differential equation in eqn (17) is,,

$$\rho = e^{-\int \frac{1}{H-l} dl} [\int -e^{\int \frac{1}{H-l} dl} \frac{k}{lg(H-l)} dl + C] \quad \dots (19)$$

Solving for the integrating factor,

$$e^{\int \frac{1}{H-l} dl} = e^{-\ln(H-l)}$$

Substituting the integrating factor, we have,

$$\rho = \frac{1}{e^{\ln(H-l)}} \left[\int -e^{\ln(H-l)} \frac{k}{lg(H-l)} dl + C \right] \quad \dots (20)$$

Or,

$$\rho = \frac{1}{H-l} \left[\int -(H-l) \frac{k}{lg(H-l)} dl + C \right]$$

The solution for the density at different depths is given by,

$$\rho = \frac{1}{H-l} \left[-\frac{k \ln l}{g} + C \right]$$

or,

$$\rho = -\frac{k \ln l}{g(H-l)} + \frac{C}{H-l} \quad \dots (21)$$

In the above solution, C is an arbitrary constant which may be determined by using a boundary condition.

Let us determine the solution at $l = H$ (i.e. at the top surface of the liquid) where $\rho = \rho_0$ which is the density of the liquid at the surface, where it is not subjected to pressure due to its own weight.

Rearranging eqn. (19) for C,

$$C = \rho(H-l) + \frac{k \ln l}{g}$$

Now we put the limit at l approaches to H ; that is $l = H - \Delta l$ where Δl tends to 0, $(H-l) = 0$. Here ρ tends to ρ_0 .

Applying the limit for Δl equal to 0 we get a value for C,

$$C = \frac{k \ln H}{g} \quad \dots (22)$$

Substituting the value for C in eqn. (21).

$$\rho = -\frac{k \ln l}{g(H-l)} + \frac{k \ln H}{g(H-l)} \quad \dots (23)$$

IV. RESULTS

Having obtained an expression for the variation of density of a liquid with depth, it would be of interest to see, how it actually varies with depth. Data was generated using the graphing tool “Desmos”, with an arbitrary value of $k = 10000$, $H = 10$, and $g = 9.8$. All values are taken in SI units. The results are presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 Variation of density of water with depth

V. DISCUSSION

On applying the boundary condition, we get a curve where density increases with depth of liquid which is as expected. However, numerical calculations and the graphical representation of the values are not according to expectations. The expression predicts a dramatic change of density with depth. The expression fails at $l = 0$, i.e. at the bottom of the column of the liquid where we encounter a singularity in the calculated density. The fundamental assumptions in the classical approach that is the liquid is a continuum does not hold true in nature. That would imply that liquid molecules have ‘zero’ volume or under limiting pressure, the liquid could assume a ‘zero’ volume. The piling up of liquid molecules with a given mass in an infinitesimal volume result in the density reaching infinity. All liquids consist of molecules which maintain a distance between themselves. The Van der Waals force predicts that the molecules must maintain an optimum distance between themselves, the Van der Waals radii. The volume of the molecule itself can never be zero and have a finite, non-zero value, the Van der Waal’s volume. This paper shows that an approach which does not take into account the discrete inter-molecular distances fail. The bulk modulus k is assumed to be constant with pressure. However, in view of Van Der Waals radii, bulk modulus is certain to increase with pressure.

VI.CONCLUSION

The paper attempts a formulation of a problem of variation of density of a column of liquid under its own weight. The analysis carried out gives a first order linear differential equation. After application of boundary condition at the surface of the liquid, a closed form solution is obtained. On computation of values, the results obtained are counterintuitive. The breakdown of the solution is ascribed to the failure to consider the discrete nature of all liquids. The Van Der Waals radii imply that the volume can never be zero at any pressure.

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